

Project brochure, other project presentation materials and
social media

D13.3

Authors:

Distribution Level	PU
Responsible Partner	Daniela Bernardo (EUI)
Checked by WP leader [name surname]	Date: 26.02.2021 Daniela Bernardo (EUI)
Verified by the appointed Reviewers [name surname, name surname]	Date: 26.02.2021 Antonello Monti (FhG) Stephan Groß (FhG)
Approved by Project Coordinator	Date: 26.02.2021 Antonello Monti (FhG)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CI	Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 957739

Issue Record

Planned delivery date	28.02.2021
Actual date of delivery	26.02.2021
Status and version	FINAL

Version	Date	Author(s)	Notes
1.0	17.02.2021	Daniela Bernardo	
2.0	26.02.2021	Daniela Bernardo	

About OneNet

OneNet will provide a seamless integration of all the actors in the electricity network across Europe to create the conditions for a synergistic operation that optimizes the overall energy system while creating an open and fair market structure.

The project OneNet (One Network for Europe) is funded through the EU's eighth Framework Programme Horizon 2020. It is titled "TSO – DSO Consumer: Large-scale demonstrations of innovative grid services through demand response, storage and small-scale (RES) generation" and responds to the call "Building a low-carbon, climate resilient future (LC)".

While the electrical grid is moving from being a fully centralized to a highly decentralized system, grid operators have to adapt to this changing environment and adjust their current business model to accommodate faster reactions and adaptive flexibility. This is an unprecedented challenge requiring an unprecedented solution. For this reason, the two major associations of grid operators in Europe, ENTSO-E and EDSO, have activated their members to put together a unique consortium.

OneNet will see the participation of a consortium of over 70 partners. Key partners in the consortium include: already mentioned ENTSO-E and EDSO, Elering, EDP Distribution, RWTH Aachen University, University of Comillas, VITO, European Dynamics, Ubitech, Engineering, and the EU's Florence School of Regulation (Energy).

The key elements of the project are:

1. Definition of a common market design for Europe: this means standardized products and key parameters for grid services which aim at the coordination of all actors, from grid operators to customers;
2. Definition of a Common IT Architecture and Common IT Interfaces: this means not trying to create a single IT platform for all the products but enabling an open architecture of interactions among several platforms so that anybody can join any market across Europe; and
3. Large-scale demonstrators to implement and showcase the scalable solutions developed throughout the project. These demonstrators are organized in four clusters coming to include countries in every region of Europe and testing innovative use cases never validated before.

Table of Contents

1 Introduction.....	4
2 Project Promotional Materials and Templates	5
3 Social Media Channels	6

1 Introduction

As part of task 13.1. General communication and dissemination activities, the EUI as WP13 leader, together with the other project partners, defined the project corporate identity and produced the first presentation materials. The project logo was selected by the consortium during the first general assembly in October 2020 from a selection of proposals developed by the EUI. The logo aims to bring the message of the project together in a simple design that can be easily presented through a number of different mediums.

The outputs of this task are presented in the following orders:

- Project logo;
- Corporate identity guidelines;
- Project brochure; and
- Project templates (word and power point).

2 Project Promotional Materials and Templates

STYLEGUIDE

TYPESET: LEQUIRE
SF PRO DISPLAY

CMYK

 1C 22M 100Y 0K
 100C 79M 29Y 13K

RGB

 253R 199G 13B
 17R 71G 119B

COLOUR CODE

 #FDC70D
 #114777

GRAYSSCALE

- 95%K
- 25%K

MONOCHROMATIC

- 100%K

USE OF THE LOGO: **EXAMPLES**

ONENET

one network for Europe

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What is OneNet?

OneNet (One Network for Europe) is an Horizon 2020 project responding to the call “Building a low-carbon, climate-resilient future”. The project brings together a consortium of over 70 partners, including key IT players, leading research institutions and the two most relevant associations for grid operators.

Why OneNet?

While the electrical grid is moving from being a fully centralized to a highly decentralized system, grid operators have to change their operative business to accommodate for faster reactions and adaptive exploitation of flexibility. OneNet aims at performing this critical step by creating the conditions for a new generation of grid services able to fully exploit demand response, storage and distributed generation while creating fair, transparent and open conditions for the consumer. The scope of OneNet is to create a fully replicable and scalable architecture that enables the whole European electrical system to operate as a single system.

The project in brief

72

Partners

23

Countries

28

Million of euros

3

Years duration

OneNet envisions a European electricity system that provides for the seamless near real time integration of all actors across countries, optimizing the overall energy management while creating an open and fair market structure and maximizing the consumer capabilities to participate in it.

Three Pillars

Definition of a common market design for Europe

Definition of a common IT Architecture and common IT Interfaces

Verification of the proposed solutions in large field tests

How will OneNet work?

7-Step OneNet Process

1. Define new and standardized products and services starting from project experience
2. Identify appropriate market structures in support of the defined products and services
3. Design open IT architecture supported by scalable data management enabling market structures
4. Implement architecture in a reference version to be used as basis for a European deployment
5. Verify in a set of large field tests the concepts and solutions proposed by OneNet
6. Create European level consensus thanks to GRIFOn open forum with all the key stakeholders
7. Push the result of OneNet in the standardization process for a significant market uptake

Four phases

Phase 1: Defining the details of the project challenge to create a European answer to flexibility management.

Phase 2: Developing the concrete OneNet approach to create unique synergies among all system and market operators.

Phase 3: Demonstrating the proposed solutions and evaluating the project results.

Phase 4: Beyond the project, fully exploiting the results and scaling the OneNet impact.

Timeline

Demos

The complete concept of OneNet is proven in 4 cluster demos involving 15 European countries.

Northern Cluster Demonstrator (WP7)

Ireland, Norway, Sweden, Finland, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania

The Northern Demonstrator is an integrated effort by multiple TSOs and DSOs to enable market driven flexibility uptake by these networks in a coordinated way through multiple markets where liquidity can be reached due to scope or existing trading volumes. Through this demonstration, the project will be able to show mapping and management of network needs in multiple use cases over multiple networks.

Southern Cluster Demonstrator (WP8)

Greece and Cyprus

The objective of the Southern Demonstrator is to prescribe, develop, implement and evaluate two pilot projects in Greece and Cyprus dealing with balancing and congestion management challenges facing system operators in the clean energy era, in compliance with the OneNet overall architecture. The results will be evaluated to provide recommendations for future market reforms in the region and harmonization for a panEU electricity market.

Western Cluster Demonstrator (WP9)

Portugal, Spain and France

The Western Demonstrator will run in three different countries and will allow for the implementation of a wide range of flexibility mechanisms to address both DSO and TSO needs, including coordination between market mechanisms and the planning and real-time

operation of the grids. Amongst the main goals to be achieved, increasing integration of renewables and anticipating operating scenarios are relevant priorities.

Eastern Cluster Demonstrator (WP10)

Czech Republic, Poland, Hungary, Slovenia

The Eastern Demonstrator will develop an interoperable network of flexibility platforms to support the utilisation of various flexibility services, service integration and interaction, as well as the related data exchange. The development will be focused in particular on four areas: definition of new standardized flexibility services, elaboration of related market based product and grid prequalification processes, the conceptualisation of location-based service activation and the coordination of access to local and system-level services.

The Consortium

Project Coordinator

Prof. Antonello Monti, Ph.D.

Antonelo.Monti@fit.fraunhofer.de

Email: info@onenet-project.eu

Website: onenet-project.eu

Title of the Deliverable Report

DX.Y

Authors:

Distribution Level	
Responsible Partner	
Checked by WP leader [name surname]	Date:
Verified by the appointed Reviewers [name surname, name surname]	Date:
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Table of Contents

1 Introduction.....	6
2 Methodology (optional section)	7
3 Content.....	8
3.1 Sub Section 1.....	8
3.1.1 Sub-sub-section	8
4 Conclusions.....	9
5 References.....	10
6 Appendix	11

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
FSR	Florence School of Regulation

Executive Summary

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1 Introduction

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3 Content

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Figure 3.1 Sample Figure Caption for Table of Figures

Table 3.1 Sample Table Caption for Table of Tables¹

¹ Sample Footnote.

4 Conclusions

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5 References

- [1] European Commission - Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - Energy Roadmap 2050 - COM(2011) 885/2 – http://ec.europa.eu/energy/energy2020/roadmap/doc/com_2011_8852_en.pdf (last accessed: DATE)

6 Appendix

7 Glossary

This paper reflects only the author's view and the Innovation and Networks Executive Agency (INEA) is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Event Name | Date

Main Presentation title goes here with auto-resizing active for very long titles that may run over three lines

Author Name

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Agenda

- Item 1: The Template Files
 - Main Content
 - Smart Net Template
 - End Slide
- Item 2: Editing the Master Slides
- Item 3: Bringing in the Extra Column
- Item 4: Further Business

Titles can run over one or two lines depending on the needs of the slide

- 15 October 2020 - European Commission funded project “OneNet” to tackle the challenges posed to TSOs, DSOs, and Consumers in the European electricity market.
 - 15 October 2020 - European Commission funded project “OneNet” to tackle the challenges posed to TSOs, DSOs, and Consumers in the European electricity market.
 - Text here for sub-point
 - 15 October 2020 - European Commission funded project “OneNet” to tackle the challenges posed to TSOs, DSOs, and Consumers in the European electricity market.
- 15 October 2020 - European Commission funded project “OneNet” to tackle the challenges posed to TSOs, DSOs, and Consumers in the European electricity market.

Two-column layout example

- 15 October 2020 - European Commission funded project “OneNet” to tackle the challenges posed to TSOs, DSOs, and Consumers in the European electricity market.
 - 15 October 2020 - European Commission funded project “OneNet” launches to tackle the challenges posed to TSOs, DSOs, and Consumers in the European electricity market.
 - Sub-sub point
 - 15 October 2020 - European Commission funded project “OneNet” to tackle the challenges posed to TSOs, DSOs, and Consumers in the European electricity market.
 - 15 October 2020 - European Commission funded project “OneNet” to tackle the challenges posed to TSOs, DSOs, and Consumers in the European electricity market.
- 15 October 2020 - European Commission funded project “OneNet” launches on 1 October to tackle the challenges posed to TSOs, DSOs, and Consumers in the European electricity market.
 - 15 October 2020 - European Commission funded project “OneNet” launches on 1 October to tackle the challenges posed to TSOs, DSOs, and Consumers in the European electricity market.
 - 15 October 2020 - European Commission funded project “OneNet” launches on 1 October to tackle the challenges posed to TSOs, DSOs, and Consumers in the European electricity market.
 - 15 October 2020 - European Commission funded project “OneNet” launches on 1 October to tackle the challenges posed to TSOs, DSOs, and Consumers in the European electricity market.

Two-column layout example with image

- How does this work?
 - Smaller size bullet
 - Even smaller bullet

Thank You

<Presenter's Name Here>

Contact Information

Affiliation: FSR

Phone: +39

Email: john.smith@onenet-project.eu

3 Social Media Channels

The OneNet social media channels (Twitter and LinkedIn) were launched on 25 November 2020. These channels aim to raise awareness by disseminating the project’s activities and findings. The main goals are:

- Contribute to defining the project identity;
- Increase project awareness;
- Drive traffic to the project website;
- Generate new leads;
- Boost engagement of stakeholders;
- Reach out to different target audiences;
- Make specialist knowledge generated by the project accessible to the wider society;
- Build a community around OneNet;
- Monitor the reputation of the project online; and
- Disseminate the multimedia content produced by the project

